

EFFECTS OF FOOD PRICES ON HOUSEHOLD FOOD SECURITY AMONG FARMING HOUSEHOLDS IN NORTHEAST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The escalating and unstable food prices in Nigeria threaten the food and nutrition security of vulnerable populations. Understanding how rising food prices affect household food access is especially critical in Northeast Nigeria where insecurity, widespread poverty and hunger are high. Hence, this study analyzed the effect of food prices on household food security among farming households in Northeast Nigeria using socioeconomic, price and food security data from General Household Survey (GHS) wave 4 post-harvest survey by the National Bureau of Statistic (NBS). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, line graphs and binary logistic regression. The study sampled 826 households from six Northeast states, distributed as Adamawa (28.45%), Bauchi (27.48%), Taraba (16.34%), Gombe (13.56%), Yobe (8.47%) and Borno (5.69%). Results of the analysis revealed that most respondents were adult male rural household heads with large families. Binary logistic regression results show that a ₦100 increase in the prices of eggs, beef, and rice significantly reduces the probability of household being food secure by 2.62%(p=0.000), 1.59%(p=0.005), and 1.80%(p=0.000), respectively, while a ₦100 increase in fish price increases it by 1.20%(p=0.002). Additionally, a one-unit increase in household size and the age of the household head decreases the likelihood of being food secure by 8.31%(p=0.000) and 0.29%(p=0.041), respectively. In contrast, higher food expenditure increases the probability of food security by 0.4%(0.000). The study concluded that price and demographic factors influence household food security and therefore recommends that government should stabilize staple food prices, enhance household food expenditure capacity and strengthen the fish value chain.

Keywords: Food price, food security, logistic regression, farming household, Northeast Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Food security is achieved when everyone has physical, social and economic access to adequate, safe and nutritious food that satisfies their dietary requirements and personal food preferences for maintaining an active and healthy life (FAO, 2008). Food security remains a major challenge for many households in Nigeria, especially in the North-eastern geopolitical zone where agricultural productivity is constrained by insecurity (Usman *et al.*, 2024), climate stress (Mohammed Dahiru & Tanko, 2018) and frequent market disruptions (Zalkuwi *et al.*, 2024). The four pillars of food security (availability, access, utilization and stability) rely heavily on the affordability and consistency of staple food prices, which are critical to household food and nutrition security because they directly affect both farmers' production choices and their purchasing power. However, in Nigeria, food price inflation has threatened food security, particularly for net food buying households and smallholder farmers who rely on both market purchases and production for their food needs (Idisi, 2021). Similarly, a study by Jerumeh (2022) revealed that fluctuations in food commodity prices in Nigeria significantly affect national food supply and dietary energy adequacy particularly in less-resourced regions, thereby reducing access to sufficient food and limiting households' ability to make nutritious dietary choices. Agriculture remains the backbone of livelihoods in the country, yet persistent challenges such as erratic rainfall, recurrent drought, low input use continue to suppress farm productivity, making affected regions highly vulnerable to food price shocks. Furthermore, fluctuating food prices have a dual effect on farming households, as they

function both as producers and consumers of food. While higher prices can increase farmers' income from the sale of agricultural produce, they can also reduce household food access and purchasing power when farmers rely on market purchases for other essential food commodities, thereby potentially threatening household food security. Households respond to food price increases by adopting various coping strategies such as reducing food consumption, borrowing money, selling assets and seeking support from social networks to maintain household food access (Alam *et al.*, 2024; Obi-Egbedi, O., & Owosho, O. E., 2023). Although the Nigerian government has introduced several interventions aimed at stabilizing food prices nationwide; however, the overall effectiveness of these measures has been limited by several challenges and shortcomings such as persistent insecurity, poor rural infrastructure and substantial post-harvest losses continue to impair agricultural supply chains thereby sustaining food price volatility and constraining progress toward improved food affordability. Among agricultural households, particularly those engaged in cereal production in the semi-arid Northeast, fluctuations in staple cereal prices affect not only food access but also dietary quality and overall livelihood resilience. However, several studies have examined food security in Nigeria, limited attention has been given to how fluctuations in specific food prices influence household food security in Northeast Nigeria. This creates a gap in understanding the price-food security dynamics in a region that is particularly vulnerable to food insecurity. Therefore, this study aims to contribute to filling this knowledge gap by examining the effect of

food prices on household food security among farming households in Northeast Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Describe socio-economic characteristics of respondents in the study area
2. Analyze trends in selected food prices in the study area
3. Estimate effects of food prices on household food security status in the study area

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Northeast Nigeria comprises Adamawa, Bauchi, Taraba, Gombe, Yobe and Borno States. This region is the largest, covering nearly one third of Nigeria's total area. It encompasses two primary ecological zones: the semi-arid Sahel savanna in the North and the tropical West Sudanian savanna in the south. The region's climate is characterized by high temperatures year-round, while the rainy season usually occurs between June and September, bringing relatively short but intense rainfall events. The region's residents engage in farming and livestock rearing. However, agricultural productivity in the study area is faced with challenges such as insecurity and climatic shocks that has exacerbated food security issue.

Source of Data

This study used secondary data from the General Household Survey (GHS) Panel wave 4 post-harvest conducted by the National Bureau of Statistic. Food prices used were obtained from the Nigeria

Bureau of Statistics (NBS) monthly selected food price data set and represent the average monthly prices of selected commodities in each state. Moreover, some of the variables required and used for the study included the sex and age of the household head, household size and the prices of food commodities such as rice, beef, fish, plantain and eggs.

Descriptive statistic and inform of bar-chart graph were used to capture socioeconomic characteristics of respondents and the movement of selected commodity prices respectively while Logistic regression was used to analyze effects of food price changes on food security status of respondents in the study area. This study adopted Zereyesus (2025) food security baseline (2100kcal/Adult Equivalent (AE) /day); households were classified as food secure or food insecure. Household food security status according to Biam and Tavershine (2020) was compared to the base daily energy consumption recommendation of 2100kcal/AE/day. Any household that consumed 2100kcal/AE/day and above were considered food secure whereas, household that consumed less than 2100kcal/AE/day were considered food insecure. Moreover, household's food consumption data covering 105 food items was used to derive calories supply or calories intake per respondents in this study. Food quantities consumed at household level were converted to calories using the locally available food consumption table for western African (2012 and 2019). The calorie result value was divided by the number of Adult Equivalent (AE) in a household so as to obtain the per capita calorie intake and then divided by 7 days recall period to obtain per capita daily

calorie intake of the respondents. The logic model used to estimate the effects of food prices on household food security among respondents in the study area is specified as:

$$\text{Logit}(P_i) = \ln\left(\frac{P_i}{1-P_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_9 X_9 + \varepsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

P = probability that household is food secure

X₁ = Egg price (₦ per dozen),

X₂ = Fish price (₦ per kg),

X₃ = Beef price (₦ per kg),

X₄ = Rice (₦ per kg),

X₅ = Plantain (₦ per piece)

X₆ = Household size (number)

X₇ = Age of household size (years)

X₈ = Food expenditure (₦)

X₉ = distance to market (km)

β₁ ... β₉ = Parameters of the coefficients,

β₀ = Intercept or the constant term

ε₁ = Error terms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' socio-economic characteristics in the study area. The result presented in Table 1 indicate that Adamawa (28.45%) and Bauchi (27.48%) recorded the highest proportion of respondents whereas Borno (5.69%) and Yobe (8.47%) had the lowest representation. The low representation observed in Borno and Yobe could be linked to accessibility difficulties and prevailing security challenges in the two states. The study further revealed that most of the respondents were male household head (91.53%). In addition, about 84.87% of the respondents resided in rural areas while only 15.13% were from urban areas suggesting that the study largely captured rural populations where

food insecurity and economic hardship are often more pronounced. The average household size in the study area was estimated at 8 persons suggesting the prevalence of relatively large families. Nonetheless, about 22.64%, 39.59% and 37.77% of respondents had household sizes of ≤4, 5-8 and >8 members respectively. Furthermore, the age distribution of household head show that 40.44%, 22.03%, 21.07% and 16.46% of respondents fell within the age groups ≤40, 41-50, 51-60 and >60 years respectively with an average age of 47 years. The mean age of 47 years suggests that most household heads are in the economically active age group, implying that they possess the experience, energy and decision-making capacity required to manage household responsibilities and improve food security outcome (Otekunrin, 2022).

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents in the study area

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
State	Adamawa	235	28.45
	Bauchi	227	27.48
	Gombe	135	16.34
	Taraba	112	13.56
	Yobe	70	8.47
	Borno	47	5.69
Sector	Rural	701	84.87
	Urban	125	15.13
Household Head Sex	Male	756	91.53
	Female	70	8.47
Household head age mean= 47	<=40	334	40.44
	41-50	184	22.03
	51-60	174	21.07
	>60	136	16.46
Household size mean=8	<=4	187	22.64
	5-8	327	39.59
	>8	312	37.77

Source: Data Analysis, 2022

Graph of selected food price across Northeast states in Nigeria.

Figures 1 present the graph of selected food commodity prices across Northeast states. The prices shown in the graph represent the price per dozen of medium-sized eggs, plantain per piece while fish, beef and rice prices are measured per kilogram respectively. Furthermore, the chart legend from Figure 1 uses distinct colours to represent each food item: dark blue (eggs), orange (fish), light gray (rice), yellow (plantain), and light blue (beef). Taraba State recorded lowest prices of egg (N438), fish (N1055), beef (N1029) and plantain (N200) whereas Adamawa State recorded highest price for egg (N462) and fish (N1171) respectively. This suggests that egg, fish beef and plantain prices were relatively lower in Taraba State compared to other Northeast states of Nigeria whereas egg and fish prices were relatively higher in Adamawa State than the other states presented in Figures 1. The graphs also reveal that rice and plantain recorded their peak prices of N328 and N268

in Borno State respectively. This suggests that in 2019, residents in Borno State incurred higher expenditure on rice and plantain compared to residents of other Northeast states in the country. More importantly, the prices of selected food commodity vary across the study area suggesting significant price differences among the Northeast states of Nigeria. These price variations could be attributed to local production capacity, transportation costs, regional demand, market structure, insecurity and other related factors. Moreover, the graphs also reveal that fish prices are higher than beef prices across Northeast states suggesting limited local fish production, high aquaculture input costs, high transportation and preservation costs. This pattern may also be attributed to supply disruptions caused by security challenges, as well as the region's comparative advantage in livestock production which results in a relatively higher supply of beef and consequently lower beef prices across the region.

Figure 1: Graph of selected food prices across Northeast states (2019)
 Source: Data Analysis, 2022

Effects of selected food commodity prices on farming household's food and nutrition security status in the Northeast of Nigeria

The result of selected food price effects on food security status of Northeast respondents from Table 2 revealed negative sign for egg, beef, rice, household size and age of household head were statistically significant. This implies that a unit increase in household size, age of household head and the price of selected food commodities such as egg, beef and rice will likely reduce food security status among Northeast respondents. In order words, one can say that rise in price of egg, beef and rice have negative effect on food

security status of the respondents. As the price of selected food increases, there is possibility that respondents will decrease their intake and consumption. Moreover, increase in selected food price makes them expensive, not readily accessible as when the price is relatively cheap and less consumed and this will in turn obstruct food and nutrition security in the study area.

Egg: Table 2 revealed that a N100 increase in the price of eggs per dozen reduces the probability of being food secure by 2.62 percentage points, ceteris paribus and it is statistically significant at 1% level. This suggest that there will be less consumption of egg and its products which are essentially meant for normal growth. As a

result of egg price hike, this scenario can likely worsen food security condition among respondents in the study area. This is consistent with the finding of Alsaad and Al-Mahish (2024) that found that increases in egg prices significantly reduce protein, fat and calorie intake derived from egg consumption thereby affect dietary quality and food security. Similarly, fluctuations and increases in egg prices have been identified as factors influencing household food consumption patterns and overall food affordability which may contribute to food insecurity when staple protein source became expensive for households, particularly those on low income (Conrad *et al.*, 2019).

Rice: A N100 increase in rice price per kg from Table 2 reduces the probability of being food secure by 1.80 percentage points among respondents under study. This implies that negative relationship exists between rice price and food security. The negative effects of rice price on food security reflects the importance of rice as a major staple food in Nigeria. Rising rice prices increase household food expenditure and reduce purchasing power, particularly for low-income rural households that depend partly on market purchases. Similar findings have been reported in studies on food price inflation in sub-Saharan Africa (Amolegbe *et al.*, 2021; Obayelu, 2022). Additionally, increase in rice price in Northeast zone increases the chances of respondents to reduce rice complements (cheese, locust (fara), fish, meat and so on) that would have improved their food security status.

Beef: Result from Table 2 also revealed that a N100 increase in beef price per kilogram reduces the probability of being food secure by 1.59 percentage points, *ceteris paribus* and it is statistically significant at 1%. The

negative relationship between beef price and food security can be explained by the fact that meat products are relatively expensive protein sources in Nigeria though cattle were reared most in Northern part of the country but demanded and consumed more in southern part. Therefore, increase in beef prices reduce households' ability to purchase adequate quantities of animal protein thereby worsening food security outcome. This is consistent with the findings of Katuka *et al.* (2025) and Anchovur *et al.* (2024) that have shown rising food prices increases the likelihood of food insecurity and reduce the quantity and quality of food consumed by households.

Fish: Conversely, Table 2 result shows that a N100 unit increase in the price of fish per kg increases the probability of respondent's being food secure by 1.20 percentage points and it is statistically significant at 1%. The positive relationship between fish price and household food security, though seemingly counterintuitive, may reflect important **income effects among fish-producing households and actors within the fish value chain**. In Northeast Nigeria, a substantial proportion of households engage in fishing, fish farming, processing, or marketing activities, particularly around water bodies such as Lake Chad. For these households, an increase in fish prices translates into **higher income rather than higher consumption costs**, thereby improving their purchasing power and overall food security status. This aligns with the farm household theory, which posits that households are both producers and consumers, and thus benefit from favorable output price increases (Singh, *et al.*, 1986). Empirical evidence indicates that although rising food prices typically reduce welfare among net buyers, they can

benefit net sellers and producers through income gains that may offset higher consumption costs (Adekunle *et al.*, 2020). Consistent with this, studies show that increases in the prices of commodities produced by households can enhance welfare and food security by boosting income (Bellemare *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, participation in fishing has been shown to significantly improve household income and livelihoods, reinforcing the role of fish-related activities in enhancing food security (Wake *et al.*, 2022)

Household size: The household size result shows that a one-unit increase in household size reduces the probability of household being food secure by 8.31 percentage points and it is statistically significant at 1% level. The negative effect of household size on food security found in this study may be attributed to increased consumption pressure associated with larger families. As the number of household members increases, available food and financial resources must be shared among more individuals, which reduces per capita food availability and increases the risk of food insecurity, particularly in resource-constrained rural households (Abdu *et al.*, 2023; Ojeleye *et al.*, 2014). In many Nigerian households, especially in rural areas, larger family sizes often lead to greater dependency burdens on limited income earners, thereby weakening the household's capacity to maintain adequate food consumption and nutritional intake (Oladeji *et al.*, 2024). Similarly, empirical studies in Nigeria indicate that large family sizes, particularly among low-income families, significantly reduce household food security by decreasing the per capita food availability and increasing pressure on limited household income and food resources (Olayemi, 2012).

Food expenditure: The study found that an increase in food expenditure reduces the probability of household being food secure by 0.04 percentage points and the effect is statistically significant at the 1% level, suggesting that households that spend more on food are more likely to be food secure. This is consistent with the findings of Mekonnen *et al.* (2021) which revealed that household with higher food expenditures had better dietary quality and reduced food insecurity because it allows them to purchase more nutrient-dense foods which are essential for a balanced diet. Similarly, Zhai *et al.* (2025) opined that higher food expenditure reduces reliance on cheap, high-calorie foods which are often associated with poor health factor and food insecurity syndrome. Furthermore, Alam *et al.* (2024) noted that increased food expenditure provides households with a buffer against food price shocks, enabling them to maintain their food consumption even during time of scarcity. Nevertheless, it is worthy to note that evidence from other studies suggests that increasing food expenditure is an important strategy for improving household food security, particularly in low-income settings where higher spending capacity enables households to purchase sufficient and more diverse foods (Amao *et al.*, 2023; Smith & Subandoro, 2007). However, it is also important to note that simply increasing food expenditure doesn't always guarantee food security. Factors like income level, food prices and cultural preferences play a role too.

Household head age: Table 2 result indicate that a one-year increase in the age of the household head reduces the probability of being food secure by 0.29 percentage points, and it is statistically significant at 5% level. The negative

relationship between the age of the household head and household food security suggests that as household heads grow older, their capacity to engage in labour-intensive agricultural activities declines. In Northeast Nigeria, where farming remains the primary livelihood and is largely dependent on manual labour, older household heads may experience reduced productivity, limited ability to cultivate large farm areas, and lower adoption of improved agricultural technologies (Owusu, 2011). These factors can decrease both food production and household income, thereby lowering the probability of achieving food security. In addition, older household heads often have larger and more dependents, increasing the burden on available resources. This is consistent with studies of Derso *et al.* (2021) and Dula (2019) which found that households are more likely to experience food insecurity as the number of dependents increases. Similarly, Ibeagwa

et al. (2020) reported an inverse relationship between age of household head and household food security status. Moreover, older household heads are more vulnerable to insurgences shocks, face health constraints, have reduced access to credit and market opportunities, further limiting their ability to secure adequate food for the household.

Also, the likelihood ratio Chi-square statistic is statistically significant (Prob>chi2 = 0.0000), indicating that the selected food price and socio-economic variables jointly influence food security. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. Although, the pseudo R² value of 0.1656 suggests modest explanatory power (16.56%). The low pseudo R² value are common in cross-sectional logit models and the overall model remain statistically significant.

Table 2: Effects of Selected food commodity prices and socioeconomic characteristics on household's food security status in Northeast

Food prices and socioeconomic characteristics	Dy/dx	Std. Error	P> z
egg	-0.0262 ***	0.0044	0.000
fish	0.0120 ***	0.0039	0.002
beef	-0.0159 ***	0.0057	0.005
rice	-0.0180 ***	0.0046	0.000
plantain	-0.0014	0.0024	0.560
Household size	-0.0831 ***	0.0140	0.000
Age of the household head	-0.0029 **	0.0014	0.041
Food expenditure	0.0004 ***	0.0001	0.000
Distance to market	-0.0009	0.0006	0.125

Number of obs = 826
 LR chi2(9) = 188.36
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 Log likelihood = -474.6692
 Pseudo R2 = 0.1656

Notes: The number of observations for Northeast zone in the above Table is 826 with *, **, *** statistically significant at 10%, 5%, and 1% level, respectively using P-values

Source: Data Analysis, 2022

CONCLUSION

The study found that majority of the respondents were adult male rural household heads residing in rural areas and managing relatively large family sizes. The study concluded that food prices differ across the Northeast states, with Taraba State recording the lowest prices for most selected food crops, reflecting regional differences in market conditions. Additionally, household food security is significantly influenced by both economic and demographic factors, as increases in beef, egg and rice prices, household size and the age of the household head reduce the likelihood of food security, while higher fish prices and greater food expenditure enhance household food security.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made to help achieve food security in the study area. Government should **stabilize prices of staple foods, particularly rice, by providing sufficient support and boosting production** to protect both consumers and producers from adverse price fluctuations. Government should **strengthen the fish value chain** by supporting production, processing, storage and marketing to increase incomes and enhance food security.

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